

SCIENTIFIC AND CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS OF DEVELOPING SPIRITUAL AND MORAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PEDAGOGUES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13911707>

Abstract: The article examines the theoretical and methodological foundations and effectiveness of developing the moral and ethical competence of future pedagogues, the improved methodical foundations and technological system of developing the moral and ethical competence of future pedagogues. Also, spiritual and moral competence and its importance in training future pedagogues was analyzed.

Key words: technology, competence, improvement, pedagogical, technological, model, didactic, spiritual-ethical competence, cognitive, active, result, form, method, tool, assessment, pedagogical experiment.

INTRODUCTION. Education of the young generation depends, first of all, on the professional skills of the pedagogue. At this point, it can be noted that the future and prospects of the country largely depend on the teacher, his level, preparation, selflessness, attitude to teaching and education work. A teacher can be a devotee of his profession only if he perfectly masters the norms of professional ethics and manners.

Today, the fact that such dedication is more important than ever increases the relevance of scientific research in this field. In particular, the requirements for the level of professional training and moral education of students of higher educational institutions of pedagogy require conducting scientific research in this regard.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. G.V. Izbullayeva, M.E. Ismoilova, V. Karimova, U. Mahkamov, N. Dj. Mahmudova, B. Sh. Mirzaolimov, O. Musurmonova, S. Nishonova, Sh. S.H. Olimov, N. Kh. Oripova, N. Ortikov, Sh. S. Shodmonova, Sh. Kurbanov, M. Kuronov, A. Haidarov, Sh. T. Halilov, J. Hasanboyev, O. Hasanboyeva; issues of spiritual, ethical and professional training of future specialists N.E. Azimova, M.E. Ahmedova, Z. Ismoilova, Sh. Q. Mardonov, G.I. Mahmutova, N.M. Ochilova, Sh. Rayimov, B. Kh. Rahimov, Z.T. Saliyeva, O'. Q. Utanov, N.M. Egamberdiyeva conducted scientific research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Goodness is the basis of all spiritual and moral qualities. In order to raise a socially active, spiritually mature person, first of all, it is necessary to form good feelings in young people. In the reforms being carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is possible to see the works being carried out for the sake of goodness. The attention paid by our government to the field of education puts the task of raising young people who love the Motherland, have faith, benevolent, intelligent, honest, clean, humane, philanthropic, and morally competent. Only young people who can embody these qualities can become highly moral, spiritually mature, socially active individuals. The following thoughts of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev on raising the morale of young people are noteworthy: "Today, when the world is rapidly changing and various new threats and dangers are emerging that lead to stability and strong development of nations, it is more important than ever to pay attention to spirituality and enlightenment, moral education, and the desire

of young people to acquire knowledge and maturity. is also important. "Education and enlightenment are the main factors of human well-being, they encourage people to be kind, generous and patient."

Five important initiatives in the social, spiritual and educational spheres put forward by our honorable President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev play an important role in raising the spirituality of young people and organizing their free time in a meaningful way. These are the following:

the first initiative is to increase the interest of young people in music, painting, theater and other types of art, to help them show their abilities;

the second initiative is to provide the necessary conditions for physical training and sports for young people;

the third initiative is to improve the skills of the population and young people in using computer technologies and the Internet;

the fourth initiative is to raise the morale of young people, widely promote reading among them;

the fifth initiative is to create additional opportunities for employment of women.

As a result of the systematic implementation of these five initiatives, especially the first and fourth initiatives, it will be possible to improve the spirituality of young people and achieve high results in their spiritual and moral education. In this regard, a number of competitions and educational events are regularly organized among students of pedagogical higher education institutions. Students show their abilities and take an active part in the events.

As a part of spiritual and moral education, a number of moral categories such as happiness, conscience, duty, justice, honor, love, goodness, glory, faith, loyalty are formed in students as a result of the formation of spiritual and moral knowledge. Qualities such as patriotism, honesty, hard work, humility, selflessness begin to emerge in a student who has mastered spiritual and moral knowledge. A student with these qualities consciously fulfills the requirements of moral standards, respects national and universal values, i.e. spiritual heritage, customs and traditions. However, having knowledge about moral and ethical standards, understanding them, and developing good qualities does not mean that the student is educated in a moral and ethical way. When the qualities of humanity are reflected in life experiences and clearly manifested in the activity of a person entering into relationships, this determines the level of his education.

In the process of education, the formation of spiritual and moral qualities in young people, the motivation to arouse their feelings towards events, people, and their own behavior will be effective only if educational activities are organized systematically. In this regard, educational activities related to the formation of behavior are considered important. Accordingly, the system of activities and relationships that encourages and stimulates the formation of moral and moral qualities is considered important.

The educational activities organized in the process of spiritual and moral education consist of a chain of behavior related to behavior and play an important role in students' learning of the essence of moral norms and principles, their understanding and practical application.

For the development of society, first of all, it is necessary to educate a morally and ethically competent, socially active person, as well as to focus on raising the level of education of young people. Because it is impossible to imagine the development of society without

morally educated individuals. In the spiritual and moral education of young people, first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the roots of the history and spirituality of our nation. In Turonzamin, it is necessary to achieve a deep understanding of the youth that human spiritual perfection, education of moral qualities has been the focus of attention of our ancestors since time immemorial.

Based on the analysis of the conducted scientific research, it is appropriate to clarify the stages of development of moral and moral qualities in students of higher educational institutions of pedagogy.

It is desirable to develop spiritual and moral qualities in students at specific stages. In this, first of all, it is necessary to be able to set the goals and tasks of spiritual and moral education correctly, to determine the content of the work, and to organize a systematic approach to achieve the goal.

The purpose of spiritual and moral education was defined as follows: training of professionally competent specialists with moral and moral qualities as a result of education and training carried out on the basis of consistency in pedagogical higher education institutions.

The following tasks are taken into account in the spiritual and moral education of students: 1) finding ways to achieve the goal of spiritual and moral education at each stage of continuous education; 2) spiritual and moral education of young people through various means of influence in the educational process; 3) use of personal methods and tools, modern information technologies in spiritual and moral education; 4) conducting questionnaire surveys and recording the results in order to determine the level of moral education of young people; 5) to achieve the training of a competent socially active specialist with spiritual and moral qualities.

CONCLUSION. In order to organize socio-pedagogical activities, it is important to implement individual-oriented educational technologies and cooperative education in the process of teaching the subject "Methodology of Pedagogical Science" in higher educational institutions of pedagogy. Through these educational technologies, an opportunity to achieve socialization of the student's personality is created.

When it comes to socialization of a person, it is necessary to reveal the meaning of the concept of socialization. In the encyclopedic dictionary of philosophy, the concept of "socialization" is defined as "the process of assimilation of the system of knowledge, norms and values that allows a person to live in society." Therefore, it is important for students to acquire knowledge about the moral and ethical categories, norms, value system, which are necessary for entering into social relations, and to improve the skills of using them in practical activities.

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